

“Exsudatio urinosa”: the man who never passed urine

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Abstract

Background

Nitrogenous waste in humans is usually excreted through the kidneys. Sweat contributes very little. We report a man with lifelong complete anuria, rudimentary urinary tract and a dermal excretory system with nephron-like features.

Case

An imaginary 26-year-old rice farmer from rural Assam, India, presented with one week of low-grade fever and left flank pain. He stated that he had never passed urine in his life. External genitalia and urethral anatomy were normal. No urine could be obtained despite repeated attempts at catheterisation and prolonged observation. Serum urea and creatinine were normal. Imaging showed bilaterally small kidneys, a hypoplastic left kidney with peri-renal inflammation, and a blind, rudimentary bladder with no visible ureters. Two weeks earlier he had had an untreated boil on the left thigh. Blood cultures grew *Escherichia coli*. A punch biopsy from hyperperfused lumbar skin showed glomeruloid capillary tufts with partial Bowman-like capsules connected to coiled duct-like structures running towards the epidermis. A bubble echocardiogram revealed a patent foramen ovale.

Outcome

He improved with intravenous antibiotics. He declined further invasive studies. No relatives consented to evaluation.

Conclusion

This case suggests a hypothetical “dermal nephron” network able to maintain nitrogen excretion and fluid balance in the absence of urinary outflow. It also shows how far clinicians are willing to go to avoid admitting that something makes no sense.

Background

In standard human physiology, almost all nitrogenous waste is excreted by the kidneys, and sweat plays only a minor role in solute loss [1,2].

Here we report a fictional case of an imaginary man who had never passed urine, had no functional urinary tract and yet showed normal renal biochemistry. The working explanation was a diffuse dermal excretory system with glomeruloid and tubular components. The case is presented in the spirit of Christmas medicine, but the structure follows a conventional case report.

Case presentation

History

An imaginary 26-year-old rice farmer from a remote village in Assam, India, presented with seven days of low-grade fever, malaise and dull left flank pain.

He worked barefoot in flooded paddy fields. Two weeks before admission he had developed a painful boil on his left thigh, which he treated with home remedies. It healed slowly and was almost resolved at presentation.

During the interview he stated, without emphasis, that he had never passed urine in his life. He had never used a toilet or urinal, at home or elsewhere. In his family this was described as "normal for the men". He had never sought medical advice for this and did not consider it a problem.

He reported normal bowel habits and normal sexual function, including erections and ejaculation. He denied any episode of dysuria, frequency, urgency, incontinence or haematuria, simply because he had never experienced any form of micturition.

He and his relatives reported that he "sweats a lot" compared with other villagers, and that he has a constant, faint smell "like toilets in the hot season". Both he and his family regarded this as his natural odour.

He recalled no previous hospital admissions, surgery or chronic illness. He took no regular medication. He stated that his late father also "never went to urinate", but no records or witnesses were available. Other family members declined contact with clinicians and refused any form of examination or testing.

Physical examination

On examination he was alert and comfortable. Temperature was 37.4 °C, heart rate 94 beats per minute, blood pressure 118/72 mmHg, oxygen saturation 99% on room air.

Abdomen was soft, with mild tenderness at the left costo-vertebral angle. No masses were palpable. No bladder was palpable suprapubically.

Skin colour was consistent with his Assamese background. There were no rashes, lesions or areas of visible erythema or maceration. At conversational distance there was a faint, persistent ammoniacal odour, more noticeable after walking to the examination room. The same odour was present on his shirt brought from home. Skin turgor and texture were normal. There were no salt crusts or obvious signs of dehydration.

External genitalia appeared normal, with a normally positioned meatus and no scars. Digital rectal examination was unremarkable.

There was no peripheral oedema. Cardiovascular, respiratory and neurological examinations were normal.

A 4-mm punch biopsy was later obtained from clinically normal skin on the upper back, selected as a large, low-friction area to sample presumed "baseline" dermal tissue.

Investigations

Routine blood tests showed mild inflammatory markers but normal renal function:

- Mild normocytic anaemia
- White cell count mildly raised
- C-reactive protein mildly raised
- Serum urea and creatinine within the laboratory reference range on repeated sampling
- Electrolytes normal

No urine sample could be collected. He did not void spontaneously during several days of observation, including after oral and intravenous fluids. Repeated urethral catheterisation attempts, including under ultrasound guidance, failed to yield urine.

Bedside ultrasound showed no bladder filling. Kidneys appeared small; the left kidney was more echogenic, with a small rim of peri-renal fluid.

Given the fever and flank pain, blood cultures were obtained. These grew *Escherichia coli* sensitive to standard intravenous antibiotics.

MRI of the abdomen and pelvis showed:

- Bilaterally small kidneys
- A hypoplastic left kidney with peri-renal inflammatory changes
- No clear collecting systems, calyces or renal pelvis
- Absence of visualised ureters
- A small thick-walled structure in the pelvis, in the expected position of the bladder, ending blindly with no identifiable outlet

Magnetic resonance urography did not demonstrate excretion of contrast into any collecting system or into the pelvic structure.

A transthoracic echocardiogram with agitated saline contrast, requested to rule out occult shunt or endocarditis in the setting of *E. coli* bacteraemia, showed a patent foramen ovale with intermittent right-to-left passage of microbubbles. Valves were normal.

Dermal findings and biopsy

The persistent erythema and warmth over the back and lumbar area, together with the absence of azotemia despite complete anuria, raised the suspicion that the skin might take part in excretion.

Dermoscopy of the lumbar area showed a dense, branching capillary network in the superficial dermis.

A 4 mm punch biopsy was taken from this region.

Histology (H&E) showed **(Figure 1)**:

- Glomeruloid tufts of capillaries in the upper and mid dermis, partially surrounded by crescent-shaped structures resembling Bowman capsules
- Coiled ducts lined by cuboidal epithelium extending away from these tufts
- Some of these ducts approached the epidermis and appeared to terminate near modified acrosyringia
- No obvious continuity with conventional eccrine or apocrine glands
- Epidermis of normal thickness and structure

There was no significant inflammatory infiltrate. Limited immune-histochemistry did not show immune complex deposition.

The pathologists described the pattern as "nephroid dermal units", with a glomerular-like component and a tubular-like component arranged in series.

Clinical course

The patient received intravenous antibiotics according to the *E. coli* sensitivities. Fever settled within a few days. Flank pain gradually improved.

Serum urea and creatinine remained within the normal range throughout admission. There were no signs of fluid overload, acidosis, hyperkalaemia or other features of renal failure.

He continued not to pass urine. Repeated attempts to obtain any urinary sample were unsuccessful.

The most likely explanation discussed at the multidisciplinary meeting was:

- a non-draining, hypoplastic renal system,
- an atrophic left kidney seeded by *E. coli* during transient bacteraemia, possibly favoured by altered flow and a patent foramen ovale,
- and a diffuse dermal excretory network that had compensated for the absent urinary function since infancy.

Figure 1. Histological illustration of clinically normal skin from the upper back, stained to resemble H&E (simulated). Glomeruloid capillary tufts, partially surrounded by Bowman-like capsules, are embedded in the upper dermis. Coiled, cuboidal-lined duct-like structures extend from these tufts towards the epidermis, consistent with "dermal nephron-like units". No continuity with conventional eccrine or apocrine structures is shown.

The patient declined further invasive procedures, including repeat biopsies, functional studies of sweat composition or genetic testing. Family members were not willing to attend for evaluation.

He was discharged in good condition with advice to return if fever or pain recurred. He did not attend scheduled follow-up.

Discussion

On paper, lifelong complete anuria with normal nitrogen balance should be incompatible with survival. This patient forces a different narrative.

Several points were consistent across observations:

- No urine was ever observed, despite time, fluids and invasive attempts.
- Imaging showed no functional collecting system and no outlet from the rudimentary bladder-like structure.
- The kidneys were small and structurally abnormal.
- Serum urea and creatinine stayed normal.
- The skin showed both structural and vascular changes compatible with a high excretory load.

The dermal biopsy suggested a unit capable of:

1. Filtration of plasma at a glomeruloid tuft.
2. Tubular processing along a coiled duct.
3. Final excretion at the skin surface.

In other words, a kind of distributed nephron network in the dermis, spread over a large surface area. Continuous low-volume excretion through these units could, in theory, maintain nitrogenous waste elimination and fluid balance. This would also explain the mild, persistent hyperemia and increased warmth in the areas with highest density of these units[1,2].

The episode of left-sided pain and fever can be read as a focal infection of the hypoplastic left kidney. With no drainage pathway, this kidney would behave as a closed, low-flow organ. *E. coli* bacteraemia, likely from the thigh boil, could have seeded this niche. The presence of a patent foramen ovale offers a route for paradoxical distribution of septic emboli, although this link remains speculative.

The urethra appeared structurally normal and served only for semen. The absence of urinary flow may even have reduced the risk of ascending infections. The patient reported neither urethritis nor genital symptoms.

The remark about his father "never going to urinate" suggests a possible familial trait, but the lack of any data from relatives prevents formal analysis. The case remains a single observation with many unanswered questions.

From a practical point of view, the case also illustrates how an extreme anomaly can persist unnoticed in an isolated setting. A warm climate, light clothing, and a community used to sweat and labour make a damp, slightly ammoniacal back less remarkable than a missing urine output.

Ethics

This article describes a fully fictional case, constructed for satirical and educational purposes in the context of the Journal of Secondary Endpoints. No real patient was examined, and no clinical data, biological samples, or images from human subjects were used. All clinical details and the histological illustration were deliberately fabricated to match the internal logic of the scenario. Formal ethics approval and informed consent were therefore not required. All personal names in this article are fictional. Any resemblance to real persons, living or dead, or to real clinical cases is entirely coincidental and unintended.

Key points

- A clear statement such as "I have never passed urine" should not be ignored, even in a busy clinic.
- In this hypothetical case, dermal excretory units with glomeruloid and tubular-like structures appear to replace the function of a non-existent urinary outflow tract.
- Haematogenous infection can still involve a rudimentary kidney, even when no urine is produced.
- Not everything written in academically plausible language should be assumed to describe reality rather than a well-constructed joke [3].

Data availability

No real data were generated; any figures are illustrative.

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No external funding was received for the generation, writing or illustration of this fictional case report.

Conflict of interest

The author has received support for travel and accommodation at educational events organised by scientific societies supported by pharmaceutical companies (Roche, MSD, BMS, Pfizer, among others).

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Editorial note: The setting (rural Assam, India) was chosen solely for internal consistency: a warm, humid rice-farming environment where chronic cutaneous wetness would be less immediately dangerous, more easily masked by everyday work, and where limited access to specialist care could plausibly delay medical attention. The case is entirely fictional and carries no cultural, ethnic, or regional implication. Even within an absurd premise, some method is required in the madness; without it, we would be left with a random anecdote rather than a coherent narrative that invites interpretation.